

In search of Transparency and Good Governance: The Curious & Poignant Case of India's North East

Author: Ayona Bhaduri

Designation: Independent Research Scholar

Qualification: Master of Arts, Public Administration

Affiliation: ICH Fellow, Sangeet Natak Akademi; Junior Research Fellow, Ministry of Culture, Govt of India; Member, International Dance Council CID, UNESCO

The Epoch making discoveries made by the Archaeological Survey of India in the 1920s, at the city sites of Harappa in West Punjab and Mohenjodaro in Sind, both located in present Pakistan, have revealed that in the third millennium BC a full fledged civilisation, age old and stereotyped with many millenniums of human endeavour behind it, flourished on Indian soil based upon a highly developed urban economy and discipline, whose antiquity is recognised to be at par with those of Mesopotamia, Iran and Egypt. About it, Professor Childe writes,

The Indian civilisation represents a very perfect adjustment of human life to a specific environment that can only have resulted from years of patient effort. And it has endured; it is already specifically Indian and forms the basis of modern Indian culture.

That it was highly advanced socially, economically and culturally, is evident not only from the sophisticated town planning, civil amenities and administration but also from the artefacts recovered from the excavations of the twin cities – Harappa and Mohenjodaro. Regular grid-like alignment of lanes and streets with excellent underground drainage system, individual houses planned with advanced accommodation and sanitary amenities, magnificent public buildings like the Great Bath at Mohenjodaro and The Great Granary at Harappa, expertise in metallurgy as evident from tools and weapons so unearthed, excellent craftsmanship evident in the seals and sealings as also such figurines as a powerfully modelled bull in terracotta, an exquisite mastiff-like figure in steatite, the remarkable statuette of a dancing girl in bronze, which stands as the earliest evidence of dance in ancient India – all of these reflect the technical skill and artistic ability of the Indus Valley people. It is obvious therefore that the Indus Valley civilisation has a continuity over six thousand years or more, a continuity that is not static but changing and progressing all the time. The Indus Valley civilisation is the very foundation on which modern Indian society firmly stands.

In other words, in India good governance has remained the bedrock of its public systems since times ancient. It has been the way of living defining the mindset of the Indian people. This is further brought to prominence by the observations of overseas visitors to India.

While describing the Indian character, Megasthenes, one of the earliest Greek historians to have visited the Maurya Court in 4th century BC, noted:

All Indians are free, and none of them is a slave....They fare happily, because of their simplicity and their frugality....Since they esteem beauty, they practise everything that can beautify their appearance. Further, they respect alike virtue and truth

Another visitor to India, an Arab astronomer al-Andalusi in 1068 CE commented:

The Indians, among other nations, through the centuries and since antiquity, were the source of wisdom, justice and moderation. They were endowed with virtues of self-control, creators of sublime thoughts, universal fables, rare inventions and remarkable concepts.

In 1882 while delivering a lecture on ‘Character of the Hindus’ the great German scholar Friedrich Max Muller observed:

It is surely extremely strange that whenever, either in Greek, or in Chinese, or in Persian, or in Arab writings, we meet with any attempts at describing the distinguishing features in the national character of the Indians, regard for truth and justice should always be mentioned first.

Finally, it is in the words of Thomas Munro, a governor of Madras in 1841, that we find the best defence of the Indian character when he speaks emphatically thus:

If a good system of agriculture, unrivalled manufacturing skill, a capacity to produce whatever can contribute to convenience and luxury; schools established in every village for teaching reading, writing, and arithmetic; the general practice of hospitality and charity among each other; and above all, a treatment of the female sex full of confidence, respect, and delicacy, are among the signs which denote a civilised people, then the Hindus are not inferior to the nations of Europe; and if civilisation is to become an article of trade between England and India, I am convinced that England will gain by the import cargo.

Governance signifies people-centric administration that establishes quality relationship between the government and the governed, leading to the overall growth and development of its people. Human development is perceived today not merely as a measure of the rise or fall of national income but as a process of creating a suitable environment that facilitates its people in leading long, healthy, productive and creative lives. This is made possible by effective and efficient processes of governance, a crucial aspect that is termed Good Governance.

Good governance aims at enhancing the quality of life, strives for maximum good for the maximum number of people through efficient governing processes involving empowerment, participation, accountability, equity and justice. Without public institutions being transparent, accountable and capable of making policies and laws that help manage both the political life and the markets of a country in an open and just way, quality of life cannot improve and therefore development cannot hold a steady, if not an upward, slope in the graph projecting its sustainability.

And to hold the line steady, it is necessary to follow certain parameters which are identified as the basic characteristics of Good Governance. These include –

- 1) Participation – Considered to be the core of Good Governance, it is facilitated by governments ensuring requisite freedom to its people such that they can articulate and represent their interests which gets reflected in policies and programmes

- 2) Rule of Law – For a government to be successful, it needs continuous guidance of a fair legal framework that is supported by appropriate enforcement machinery, independent judiciary, which instils confidence in its people
- 3) Transparency – Accessibility of information used by the government for decision making, to those affected by such decisions so that they can comprehend better as also monitor government activities to curb exploitation
- 4) Responsiveness – Responding to the needs of the people so as to make decisions that are people centric and people friendly within reasonable limits
- 5) Equity - Making sure that all members of a society share equal rights and benefits, and none is marginalised from its mainstream activities toward development
- 6) Effectiveness and Efficiency – Resources need to be utilised efficiently and effectively so as to meet the societal needs and demands
- 7) Accountability – Occupying a central place in Good Governance, this norm ensures answerability of functioning bodies of both public and private sectors and also the proper enforcement of correct procedure in case of violation of certain laid down norms

It is only when these characteristics reinforce each other, Good Governance as a norm is successful and becomes a salient feature of public administration aimed at overall development of the society at large and of all aspects of human life.

The founding fathers of the Indian Constitution, believing that India through her age-old ability to synthesize cultures, could become modern, yet remain Indian, established within the Constitution's framework both the nation's ideals and the institutions and processes for achieving them. The ideals were national unity and integrity and a democratic and equitable society, such a new society that was to be achieved through a socio-economic revolution pursued with a democratic spirit using constitutional, democratic institutions.

The Indian constitution is first and foremost a social document permeated by the aim of national renaissance with the core of the commitment to this social and its associated economic revolution enshrined in Parts III and IV, in the Fundamental Rights and Directive Principles of State Policy. These essentially form the conscience of the Constitution as also the very foundation of Good Governance.

The Fundamental Rights in the Indian Constitution are divided into seven parts: the Right to Equality, the Right of Freedom, the Right against Exploitation, the Right to Freedom of Religion, Cultural and Educational Rights, the Right to Property, and the Right to Constitutional Remedies. The Rights lay down that the state is to deny no one equality before the law. All citizens are to have the right of religion, assembly, association, and movement within the territory of India. No person is to be deprived of his life, liberty, or property, except in accordance with the law. Minorities are to be allowed to protect and conserve their language, script, and culture. Further, various means are provided whereby the citizen can move the Supreme Court and other courts for the enforcement of the Fundamental Rights.

The Directive Principles aim at making the Indian masses free in the positive sense, free from the passivity engendered by centuries of coercion by society and by nature, free from the dire

physical conditions that had prevented them from fulfilling their best selves. And to achieve this, the State is to apply the precepts contained therein when making laws. These principles are not justiciable, a court cannot enforce them, but they are to be, nevertheless, fundamental in the governance of the country. The very essence of the Directive Principles lies in Article 38, which, echoing the Preamble, states:

.....the State shall strive to promote the welfare of the people by securing and protecting as effectively as it may a social order in which justice, social, economic, and political, shall inform all the institutions of the national life.

One can therefore find within the framework of the Indian Constitution the guiding principles that would make the administrative system of the country not only transparent and accountable but also equipped adequately to deliver good governance to its people.

Despite this, safeguarding of these Rights and Principles is found to be starkly lacking in the attitude and treatment accorded to the people of the North East of the country.

The north eastern region of India is often described as the cultural mosaic of India consisting of diverse tribal communities, linguistic, and ethnic identities. The region, connected to the mainland India with the 22 km long “Chicken-Neck Corridor”, consists of eight states and has international border with five neighbouring countries. In the international scene, it is a strategic location linked to South and South-East Asia. From internal security point of view, the region is known for the ‘problem states’, experiencing law and order problems, inter and intra tribal conflicts and human rights violations by the security forces.

The politics of northeast India has been and continues to be marked by ethnicity and extremism. Identity remains central to the conflict situation and these are interlinked with the question of land and territory. Demand for territorial autonomy and exercise of right to self-determination are recurrent themes in different movements. The overlapping of geographical boundary in the proposed ethnic homelands is a potential source of contest and confrontation because the traditional cultural boundary, which defined the territorial boundary with different tribes living within that territory, has been transformed by political boundaries.

Most of the ethnic assertions are due to the ethnic groups’ desperate attempts to protect their identity, culture and language. For instance, it is argued that claims to ethno-nationalism of the Bodos in Assam can be interpreted as closely intertwined with issues of institutional and social exclusion based on language politics. The movement launched by the All Bodo Students’ Union (ABSU) for the introduction of Roman script in Bodo language in place of Assamese or to replace the use of Bengali script in Manipuri language with the traditional Meitei script became a unifying force in the face of the perceived or real danger to their existence. The same holds true for the insurgent groups in Nagaland as well who did not accept the Indian Constitution, its sixth schedule meant for the North East, boycotted the first general election of 1952, and demanded the establishment of their own sovereign state – the Federal Republic of Nagaland. Supported by bordering neighbour countries, they set up an umbrella organisation under the leadership of NSCN or National Socialist Council of Nagaland. The recent highly debated Naga Pact of 2015 aimed to reconcile the Nagas with the Union Government is a

welcome step though it remains to be seen how successful its implementation is. The areas of Assam, inhabited by the Khasis, Jaintias and Garos too witnessed the movement for an autonomous state resulting in the formation of the state of Meghalaya in 1972.

Thus, the basis of ethnic assertion can be seen in two contexts.

- the tribal communities' subjective consciousness of being excluded, oppressed and marginalized.
- the process of development/modernisation/nation-building posing a conflict between modernity and tradition thereby failing to address the legitimate concerns of the people. Moreover, development has led to the unequal distribution of resources across the communities and regions.

The reasons for the emergence of social forces in the northeast include: the impact of Christianity on the socio-cultural life of the people, spread of education, etc with three major agents of change among the tribes of northeast India – the state, the civil society (of which the Church is the major element) and the market forces.

Moreover, various armed groups are involved in an organized network of extortion or indigenous network of tax collection system that sustains the militant governments, maintains their staff, security infrastructure and allied activities. The tribal people are compelled to contribute part of their income for this purpose. The nexus between politicians and militant groups is an open secret and is used to win democratic elections, settle business deals and fight political rivals. This dreadful symbiotic relationship is the biggest stumbling block to law and order, which is the responsibility of a democratically elected government. It encourages corruption and undermines the moral authority of the state.

In the case of the North East of India, one can therefore assert that though the spirit of the age favours equality, practice denies it there. Although we have won our freedom and gotten ourselves rid of slavery from British rule, a new slavery has emerged, perhaps far worse than the old, in which, in the name of individual freedom, political and economic systems exploit human beings and treat them as commodities as is obvious in the organised network of extortion so rampant there.

It then follows that if the spirit of the times demands equality, it must necessarily also demand an economic system which compliments it and more importantly, encourages it. And this should be led by political change in the direction of a democratically planned collectivism. The choice must never be between competition and monopoly, rather it should be between a monopoly that is irresponsible and private and a monopoly which is responsible and public.

The North East, as the rest of India, deserves equal and sustained attention, vision and development, both political and cultural which would be possible only when racialism is discarded from the minds of not only the people being administered but also of those administering. The sense of justice and truth must come from within, it can never be imposed from outside.

In his personal idea of India, Mahatma Gandhi highlights the issues troubling the north eastern people, and in doing so he clearly lays down the guidelines for a transparent administrative system dedicated to the delivery of good governance:

I shall work for an India in which the poorest shall feel that it is their country, in whose making they have an effective voice, an India in which there shall be no high class and low class people, an India in which all communities shall live in perfect harmony....There can be no room in such an India for the curse of untouchability or the curse of intoxicating drinks or drugs.....Women will enjoy the same right as men.....This is the India of my dreams.

When, and hopefully soon, the bureaucracy as also every public office bearer begins to orient himself with this vision, only then perhaps will the North East of India truly flourish, its people's rights and interests adequately safeguarded, and become all that the world recognises as Indian.

Kolkata, India
April 10, 2018

Reference:

Nehru Jawaharlal, *The Discovery of India*, Meridian Books UK, 1946, Print
Austin Granville, *The Indian Constitution*, Oxford University Press, 1966, Print